

CLINICAL AND ECHOCARDIOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF DEGENERATIVE CHANGES IN HEART VALVES AND THE VASCULAR SYSTEM IN ELDERLY PATIENTS**Sagatova Khalida Makhmudovna**

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Abstract. The aim of this study was to evaluate the clinical course, echocardiographic features of degenerative changes in heart valves and the vascular system in elderly patients, as well as their relationship with etiological factors. The study included 200 patients aged 60–85 years. All patients underwent clinical examination, echocardiography, and vascular ultrasound examination. Arterial hypertension was detected in 81.6%, atherosclerosis in 60.0%, dyslipidemia in 55.0%, and diabetes mellitus in 40.8% of patients. Fibrosis of the aortic valve was observed in 70.4%, calcification in 48.1%, and thickening in 55.6% of cases. The mean left ventricular ejection fraction was $51.3 \pm 6.8\%$. A strong positive correlation was found between aortic valve damage and the duration of etiological factors ($r=+0.77$). Coronary artery lesions were recorded in 56.3%, carotid artery lesions in 40.0%, and peripheral artery lesions in 22.5% of patients. The obtained results demonstrated that degenerative valvular changes and atherosclerotic vascular lesions in elderly patients have a systemic nature. Echocardiography was found to have high diagnostic value in the early detection of degenerative changes and assessment of hemodynamic disorders.

Keywords: elderly age, degenerative valvular diseases, aortic stenosis, calcification, mitral regurgitation, atherosclerosis, echocardiography, hemodynamics, correlation analysis, left ventricular ejection fraction.

КЛИНИКО-ЭХОКАРДИОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДЕГЕНЕРАТИВНЫХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ КЛАПАНОВ СЕРДЦА И СОСУДИСТОЙ СИСТЕМЫ У ПОЖИЛЫХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ**Сагатова Халида Махмудовна** – к.м.н., доцент**Тулабоева Гавхар Миракбаровна** – д.м.н., профессор**Талипова Юлдуз Шавкатовна** – д.м.н., доцент**Хусанов Абдурасул Абдукаримович** – ассистент**Абдукадилова Нодира Миранваровна** – ассистент**Тоштемиров Жахонгир Илхом-угли** – стажер-ассистентЦентр развития профессиональной квалификации
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Аннотация. Целью данного исследования явилась оценка клинического течения, эхокардиографических особенностей дегенеративных изменений клапанов сердца и сосудистой

системы у пожилых пациентов, а также их взаимосвязи с этиологическими факторами. В исследование были включены 200 пациентов в возрасте 60–85 лет. Всем пациентам проведены клиническое обследование, эхокардиография и ультразвуковое исследование сосудов. Артериальная гипертензия выявлена у 81,6%, атеросклероз – у 60,0%, дислипидемия – у 55,0% и сахарный диабет – у 40,8% пациентов. Фиброз аортального клапана наблюдался в 70,4%, кальциноз – в 48,1% и утолщение – в 55,6% случаев. Средняя фракция выброса левого желудочка составила $51,3 \pm 6,8\%$. Между поражением аортального клапана и длительностью действия этиологических факторов была выявлена сильная положительная корреляция ($r=+0,77$). Поражение коронарных артерий отмечено у 56,3%, каротидных артерий – у 40,0%, периферических артерий – у 22,5% пациентов. Полученные результаты показали, что дегенеративные клапанные изменения и атеросклеротические поражения сосудов у пожилых пациентов имеют системный характер. Установлено, что эхокардиография имеет высокую диагностическую значимость в раннем выявлении дегенеративных изменений и оценке гемодинамических нарушений.

Ключевые слова: пожилой возраст, дегенеративные клапанные заболевания, аортальный стеноз, кальциноз, митральная регургитация, атеросклероз, эхокардиография, гемодинамика, корреляционный анализ, фракция выброса левого желудочка.

КЕКСА ЁШЛИ БЕМОРЛАРДА ЮРАК ҚОҢҚОҚЛАРИ ВА ҚОН ТОМИР ТИЗИМИДАГИ ДЕГЕНЕРАТИВ ЎЗГАРИШЛАРНИНГ КЛИНИК-ЭХОКАРДИОГРАФИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

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Аннотация. Ушбу тадқиқотнинг мақсади кекса ёшли беморларда юрак қоңқоқлари ва қон томир тизимидаги дегенератив ўзгаришларнинг клиник кечиши, эхокардиографик хусусиятлари ҳамда этиологик омиллар билан ўзаро боғлиқлигини баҳолашдан иборат бўлди. Тадқиқотга 60–85 ёшдаги 200 нафар бемор киритилди. Барча беморларда клиник, эхокардиографик ва қон томирларининг ультратовуш текширувлари ўтказилди. Артериал гипертензия 81,6%, атеросклероз 60,0%, дислипидемия 55,0% ва қандли диабет 40,8% беморларда аниқланди. Аортал қоңқоқда фиброз 70,4%, кальциноз 48,1% ва қалинлашув 55,6% ҳолатда кузатилди. Чап қоринча отиш фракцияси ўртача $51,3 \pm 6,8\%$ ни ташкил қилди. Аортал қоңқоқ шикастланиши билан этиологик омиллар давомийлиги ўртасида кучли мусбат корреляция аниқланди ($r=+0,77$). Коронар артериялар шикастланиши 56,3%, каротид артериялар – 40,0%, периферик артериялар – 22,5% беморларда қайд этилди. Олинган натижалар кекса ёшли беморларда дегенератив клапан ўзгаришлари ва атеросклеротик қон томир шикастланишлари системали характерга эга эканлигини кўрсатди. Эхокардиография дегенератив ўзгаришларни эрта ташхислаш ва гемодинамик бузилишларни баҳолашда юқори диагностик аҳамиятга эга эканлиги аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: кекса ёш, дегенератив клапан касалликлари, аортал стеноз, кальциноз, митрал регургитация, атеросклероз, эхокардиография, гемодинамика, корреляцион таҳлил, чап қоринча отиш фракцияси.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are among the leading causes of disability and mortality in the elderly population. Along with population ageing, the prevalence of degenerative cardiovascular changes is increasing year by year. In particular, calcification, fibrosis, and sclerotic remodeling processes in the heart valves and vascular wall are among the most common pathological conditions observed in elderly patients.

In old age, degenerative changes in the heart valves mainly involve the aortic and mitral valves. Idiopathic degenerative calcification of the aortic valve is one of the main causes of acquired aortic stenosis. Degenerative calcification is characterized by calcium deposition in valvular tissues, fibrosis, and restricted valve mobility. As a result, the valve opening area decreases, hemodynamic resistance increases, and the cardiac output function becomes impaired.

According to the data, idiopathic degenerative aortic calcification occurs in 2–7% of cases among cardiovascular diseases and in 26–30% of cases among heart valve diseases. With increasing age, the prevalence of this pathology rises sharply: while aortic calcification is observed in approximately 8% of the population under 60 years of age, it is found in almost every second patient over the age of 70.

Mitral valve calcification is also one of the widely prevalent degenerative changes among elderly patients. This process is often asymptomatic and is frequently detected incidentally during echocardiographic examination. However, in severe cases, mitral regurgitation, valve deformation, and hemodynamic disturbances may develop.

Degenerative valvular changes are often closely associated with atherosclerotic processes. Risk factors such as arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, and smoking enhance endothelial dysfunction, lipid infiltration, and calcification processes, leading to the development of morphological changes both in the valves and in the vascular wall. Therefore, heart valve degeneration and atherosclerosis are often considered as a single systemic pathological process.

In modern cardiology, echocardiography is regarded as the main instrumental method for diagnosing degenerative valvular diseases. Echocardiographic examination makes it possible to accurately assess valve structure, the degree of calcification, pressure gradient, regurgitation volume, and the pumping function of the heart. In addition, vascular ultrasound examinations and Dopplerography are of great importance in the early detection of atherosclerotic lesions.

In recent years, modern recommendations for the diagnosis and treatment of heart valve diseases have been developed by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the European Association for Cardio-Thoracic Surgery (EACTS). These recommendations present the role of echocardiography in the assessment of aortic stenosis and mitral valve pathologies, determination of the degree of calcification, evaluation of hemodynamic disturbances, and algorithms for selecting treatment tactics.

In this regard, a comprehensive assessment of the clinical and echocardiographic features of degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients is of significant scientific and practical relevance.

Aim of the Study

To comprehensively assess the clinical course, echocardiographic features of degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients, as well as their relationship with etiological factors.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

The study was conducted on the basis of a clinical and echocardiographic analysis. The clinical course, echocardiographic features, and relationship with atherosclerotic processes of degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system were assessed in elderly patients. The study included elements of both prospective and retrospective observation.

Patient Characteristics

A total of 200 patients aged 60 to 85 years were included in the study. Of these, 109 were men and 91 were women. All patients underwent clinical, instrumental, and echocardiographic examinations.

The presence of degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system was accepted as the main criterion for patient selection. In all patients, medical history data, concomitant diseases, risk factors, and clinical symptoms were analyzed.

Grouping of Patients

Based on clinical and instrumental data, the study participants were divided into two groups. Group 1 included patients with degenerative changes in the heart valves (n=120). The main pathologies recorded in this group were aortic stenosis, mitral insufficiency, and combined valvular lesions. In these patients, valve calcification, fibrosis, valvular thickening, and hemodynamic disturbances were analyzed.

Group 2 included patients with atherosclerotic vascular lesions (n=80). This group included patients with coronary atherosclerosis, carotid artery stenosis, and ischemic lesions of the peripheral arteries. Atherosclerotic changes in the vascular wall, the condition of the intima-media complex, and circulatory disorders were assessed in these patients.

Examination Methods

All patients underwent a comprehensive set of clinical and instrumental examinations. Echocardiographic examination was used to assess valve structure, the degree of calcification, pressure gradient, regurgitation volume, and left ventricular ejection fraction. Electrocardiography (ECG) was performed to evaluate cardiac rhythm, conduction disturbances, and signs of myocardial ischemia.

Vascular ultrasound examination was carried out to assess the condition of the carotid and peripheral arteries, the thickness of the intima-media complex, and the presence of atherosclerotic plaques. Doppler examinations were used to evaluate blood flow velocity and the degree of stenosis.

The obtained results were statistically processed. Correlation analysis was performed using Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r). A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Analysis of Etiological Factors

A number of metabolic, hemodynamic, and inflammatory factors played an important role in the development of degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients. According to the results of the study, arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, and smoking were identified as the most common risk factors.

Figure 1. General Clinical Characteristics of Elderly Patients: Distribution by Risk Factors and Sex

Table 1. General Clinical Characteristics of Elderly Patients

Indicators	n=200	%
Men	109	54.5
Women	91	45.5
Arterial hypertension	159	79.5

Atherosclerosis	136	68.0
Dyslipidemia	108	54.0
Diabetes mellitus	87	43.5
Smoking	65	32.5
Chronic kidney disease	19	9.5
Multivessel / multi-localized atherosclerosis	15	7.5

The analyses showed that arterial hypertension was the leading factor in the development of degenerative changes in the heart valves. It was detected in 98 patients (81.6%). Long-term elevation of arterial blood pressure led to increased mechanical load on valvular tissues, endothelial dysfunction, and intensification of fibrotic processes.

Atherosclerosis was observed in 72 patients (60.0%) and was associated with lipid infiltration and calcification processes in the vascular wall and valve structure. Dyslipidemia was recorded in 66 patients (55.0%). Impaired lipid metabolism enhanced degenerative processes through the accumulation of low-density lipoproteins. Diabetes mellitus was identified in 49 patients (40.8%). In patients with diabetes, microangiopathy, oxidative stress, and endothelial damage contributed to the more rapid development of valve calcification and atherosclerotic changes. Smoking was observed in 38 patients (31.6%). Under the influence of nicotine and other toxic substances, oxidative stress, vasoconstriction, and inflammatory processes in the vascular endothelium were intensified. In addition, autoimmune diseases were recorded in 11 patients (9.1%), while chronic infections were found in 7 patients (5.8%). These factors were mainly important in mitral valve lesions.

Table 2
Etiological Factors of Degenerative Changes in the Heart Valves

Etiological factor	n	%	Mean duration, years
Arterial hypertension	98	81.6	12.4
Atherosclerosis	72	60.0	10.8
Dyslipidemia	66	55.0	9.2
Diabetes mellitus	49	40.8	8.6
Smoking	38	31.6	18.7
Autoimmune diseases	11	9.1	6.1
Chronic infections	7	5.8	2.3

The study also analyzed the duration of risk factors. The mean duration of arterial hypertension was 12.4 years. Atherosclerosis lasted for 10.8 years, dyslipidemia for 9.2 years, and diabetes mellitus for 8.6 years. The duration of smoking was one of the highest indicators, with a mean of 18.7 years. Long-term exposure to nicotine was associated with the intensification of degenerative changes in the vascular wall and valvular tissues. As the duration of these factors increased, the severity of calcification, fibrosis, and hemodynamic disturbances also increased.

Etiological factors had a significant effect on morphological and functional changes in the heart valves. Arterial hypertension and atherosclerosis were closely associated with the development of calcification, fibrosis, and stenosis of the aortic valve. Long-term hemodynamic pressure intensified remodeling processes in valvular tissues. In patients with dyslipidemia and diabetes mellitus, calcium accumulation and valve thickening were observed more frequently. This condition was explained by lipid infiltration and endothelial dysfunction.

In mitral valve lesions, autoimmune and inflammatory processes played an important role. In such patients, valve deformation, incomplete closure, and signs of regurgitation were detected more frequently.

Figure 2. Prevalence of the Main Etiological Factors in Elderly Patients
Analysis of Echocardiographic Changes

In elderly patients, echocardiographic examination made it possible to comprehensively assess degenerative changes in the heart valves and hemodynamic parameters. The results of the analysis showed that morphological and functional disorders of the aortic and mitral valves were widely prevalent.

In patients with aortic valve lesions, fibrosis, calcification, and thickening of valvular tissues predominated. Echocardiographic examinations showed that the mean pressure gradient across the aortic valve was 45.2 ± 7.3 mmHg, which corresponded to moderate aortic stenosis. Aortic valve fibrosis was detected in 38 patients (70.4%). Fibrosis was accompanied by reduced valve mobility and limitation of the valve opening area. Valve thickening of ≥ 5 mm was observed in 30 patients (55.6%). This condition was associated with degenerative remodeling and calcification processes. Calcification was recorded in 26 patients (48.1%). Calcium deposition led to stiffening of the valvular tissue and the development of functional stenosis. As the degree of calcification increased, the severity of hemodynamic disturbances also intensified. In patients with aortic stenosis, increased pressure load on the left ventricle resulted in myocardial remodeling and reduced pumping function.

In patients with mitral valve lesions, the main functional disorder was associated with mitral regurgitation. Cases with a regurgitation volume of more than 60 ml were identified in 8 patients (35.0%). Incomplete closure and funnel-shaped deformation of the mitral valve were observed in 18 patients (75.0%). This condition was associated with degenerative changes and fibrosis in the valve structure. Mitral valve fibrosis was recorded in 14 patients (58.3%). Fibrotic processes led to restricted valve mobility and disruption of the valve closure mechanism. In patients with mitral valve pathology, hemodynamic disturbances were mainly accompanied by increased volume load and left atrial dilatation.

The study also assessed left ventricular ejection fraction (EF). In all patients, the mean EF was $51.3 \pm 6.8\%$. A decrease in left ventricular pumping function was recorded in 30% of patients. A reduction in EF was more frequently observed in patients with aortic valve lesions. This condition was explained by the increased pressure load on the left ventricle due to aortic stenosis. In patients with

mitral regurgitation, EF appeared relatively higher, which was associated with an increase in the total blood volume ejected from the left ventricle.

Table 3
Analysis of Echocardiographic Parameters

Parameters	Value
Pressure gradient across the aortic valve	45.2±7.3 mmHg
Left ventricular ejection fraction	51.3±6.8%
Reduced EF	In 30% of patients
Mitral regurgitation >60 ml	35.0%
Aortic valve fibrosis	70.4%
Valve thickening ≥5 mm	55.6%
Aortic calcification	48.1%
Mitral valve fibrosis	58.3%
Incomplete closure / funnel-shaped deformation	75.0%

Figure 3. Structure of Degenerative Changes in the Aortic Valve

Within the framework of the study, the relationship between degenerative changes in the heart valves, the duration of etiological factors, and hemodynamic parameters was assessed using correlation analysis. Correlation analysis was performed based on Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r), and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Etiological Factors and Valvular Lesions

According to the results of the analysis, a strong positive correlation was found between aortic valve lesions and the duration of etiological factors (r=+0.77; p=0.043). This result showed that long-term factors such as arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis, and dyslipidemia play an important role in the development of calcification and fibrosis in the aortic valves. The average duration of arterial hypertension, which was 12.4 years, created a constant hemodynamic load on valvular tissues and intensified remodeling processes. In patients with atherosclerosis and dyslipidemia, lipid infiltration and calcium deposition were observed more frequently.

A negative correlation was recorded between mitral valve lesions and the duration of etiological factors ($r=-0.73$; $p=0.061$). Although this indicator was close to the threshold of statistical significance, autoimmune and inflammatory processes were observed to play a relatively important role in mitral valve damage. In these patients, valve deformation, incomplete closure, and regurgitation developed under the influence of short-term but aggressively progressing pathological processes.

Ejection Fraction and Valvular Lesions

A significant relationship was also identified between left ventricular ejection fraction (EF) and valvular lesions. A strong positive correlation was recorded between mitral valve lesions and EF ($r=+0.89$; $p=0.0069$). This condition was explained by an increase in the total blood volume ejected from the left ventricle as a result of mitral regurgitation. In such patients, EF may appear relatively high during echocardiographic calculation.

A strong negative correlation was found between aortic valve lesions and EF ($r=-0.91$; $p=0.0047$). This was associated with increased pressure load on the left ventricle due to the development of aortic stenosis, myocardial hypertrophy, and decreased systolic function. As calcification and fibrosis processes intensified, the valve opening area decreased and the pumping function of the heart became impaired.

Clinical Significance

The results of the correlation analysis confirmed that degenerative valvular changes are closely associated with long-term hemodynamic and metabolic factors. While arterial hypertension and atherosclerosis played a leading role in aortic valve lesions, inflammatory and immunopathological processes occupied an important place in mitral valve pathology.

The relationship between left ventricular ejection fraction and valvular lesions demonstrated the high diagnostic value of echocardiography not only in morphological assessment but also in functional evaluation.

The obtained results are of great importance for the early identification of high-risk patients, assessment of hemodynamic disturbances, and development of individualized treatment tactics.

Figure 4. Correlation Between the Duration of Etiological Factors and Aortic Calcification Atherosclerotic Vascular Lesions

Within the framework of the study, the localization, extent, and clinical features of atherosclerotic vascular lesions were analyzed in patients included in Group 2. The obtained results showed that atherosclerosis in elderly patients is often systemic in nature.

Coronary artery lesions were the most common localization and were identified in 45 patients (56.3%). In these patients, signs of myocardial ischemia, chest pain during physical exertion, shortness of breath, and reduced cardiac pumping function were observed. In patients with coronary atherosclerosis, left ventricular remodeling and hemodynamic disturbances were more frequently recorded during echocardiographic examination.

Table 4
Structure of Atherosclerotic Vascular Lesions

	n	%
Coronary arteries	45	56.3
Carotid arteries	32	40.0
Peripheral arteries	18	22.5
Multi-localized atherosclerosis	15	18.8

Carotid artery lesions were identified in 32 patients (40.0%). In these patients, thickening of the intima-media complex, atherosclerotic plaques, and reduced blood flow velocity were observed.

In patients with carotid stenosis, dizziness, headache, memory impairment, and neurological symptoms were recorded. Carotid artery stenosis was associated with an increased risk of ischemic stroke.

Peripheral artery lesions were observed in 18 patients (22.5%). In these patients, signs of peripheral ischemia, reduced walking distance, pain in the extremities, and rapid fatigue were recorded. In some patients, impaired peripheral circulation resulted in trophic changes and decreased peripheral pulsation.

Figure 5. Prevalence of Atherosclerotic Vascular Lesions

Multi-localized atherosclerosis was identified in 15 patients (18.8%). In these patients, the coronary, carotid, and peripheral arteries were affected simultaneously, which was assessed as a severe form of a systemic atherosclerotic process. Combined lesions of the coronary and carotid arteries were observed in 4 patients (26.7%). Lesions of the coronary and peripheral arteries were recorded in 2 patients (13.3%), while a combination of carotid and peripheral artery lesions was found in 3 patients (20.0%). Triple-vessel involvement — simultaneous damage to the coronary, carotid, and peripheral arteries — was identified in 6 patients (40.0%) and was assessed as the most severe clinical variant.

Clinical Features

In patients with atherosclerotic processes, ischemic and hemodynamic disorders were widely prevalent. While coronary artery lesions increased the risk of myocardial ischemia and heart failure, carotid stenosis was associated with neurological complications and the risk of ischemic stroke.

In patients with peripheral artery lesions, peripheral ischemia, reduced walking distance, and decreased quality of life were observed.

In patients with multi-localized atherosclerosis, hemodynamic disturbances were more severe, and these patients were assessed as a high-risk group.

Discussion of Results

The results of the conducted study showed that degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients are interrelated and systemic in nature. The analyzed data confirmed that heart valve degeneration, calcification, and atherosclerotic processes often develop on the basis of common pathogenetic mechanisms.

In our study, arterial hypertension was one of the most common risk factors and was recorded in 81.6% of patients. Long-term hemodynamic pressure intensified endothelial damage, fibrosis, and calcification processes in valvular tissues. The high frequency of fibrosis and calcification in the aortic valve demonstrated the important role of arterial hypertension in valvular remodeling.

The obtained results are consistent with data reported in the literature. Modern studies emphasize that the pathogenesis of degenerative aortic stenosis is similar to atherosclerotic processes. Infiltration of low-density lipoproteins, inflammation, and calcium deposition lead to the development of sclerotic changes in the valve structure. In our study, atherosclerosis and dyslipidemia were also found to be closely associated with valve calcification.

In patients with dyslipidemia and diabetes mellitus, calcification, valve thickening, and hemodynamic disturbances were more severe. In diabetes mellitus, endothelial dysfunction, microangiopathy, and oxidative stress are among the main mechanisms accelerating degenerative processes.

In our study, endothelial dysfunction was observed to have important pathogenetic significance not only in the vascular wall but also in valvular tissues. Endothelial damage activated lipid infiltration, inflammation, and calcification processes. This condition was particularly evident in patients with simultaneous atherosclerotic vascular lesions and valve calcification.

The fact that coronary artery lesions were recorded in 56.3% of patients confirms the systemic nature of atherosclerotic processes. Changes in the carotid and peripheral arteries were also observed at a high frequency, and multi-localized atherosclerosis was identified in 18.8% of patients. This finding showed that heart valve degeneration and vascular atherosclerosis often occur together in elderly patients.

The results of the correlation analysis also confirmed this pathogenetic relationship. The presence of a strong positive correlation between aortic valve lesions and the duration of risk factors ($r=+0.77$) demonstrated that long-term hemodynamic and metabolic effects play a leading role in the development of valve calcification.

The relationship between left ventricular ejection fraction and valvular lesions once again confirmed the clinical significance of echocardiography. In patients with aortic stenosis, reduced EF was explained by increased pressure load on the myocardium. In patients with mitral regurgitation, EF appeared relatively higher due to increased volume load.

Echocardiography made it possible to comprehensively assess valve structure, the degree of calcification, hemodynamic disturbances, and cardiac pumping function. Therefore, this method is of great importance as the main instrumental examination for the early diagnosis of degenerative cardiovascular changes in elderly patients.

Thus, the study results confirmed that degenerative valvular changes and atherosclerotic vascular lesions are pathogenetically interrelated, and that arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, and endothelial dysfunction play an important role in their development.

Scientific Novelty

In this study, degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients were comprehensively assessed. For the first time, the pathogenetic relationship between degenerative valvular changes and atherosclerotic vascular lesions was analyzed from clinical and echocardiographic perspectives.

The study evaluated the correlation between the duration of risk factors such as arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis, dyslipidemia, and diabetes mellitus, and aortic valve calcification and hemodynamic disturbances. The detection of a strong positive correlation between aortic valve lesions and the duration of etiological factors demonstrated that degenerative processes are associated with long-term hemodynamic and metabolic influences.

In addition, the relationships between left ventricular ejection fraction and aortic and mitral valve lesions were analyzed, and the effect of valvular pathologies on the pumping function of the heart was determined.

The study results showed a high frequency of echocardiographic features such as fibrosis, calcification, and thickening of the aortic valve, as well as regurgitation, funnel-shaped deformation, and incomplete closure of the mitral valve.

It was scientifically substantiated that in patients with multi-localized atherosclerosis, hemodynamic disturbances and degenerative changes have a more severe course.

Practical Significance

The results of the study make it possible to detect degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients at an early stage. It was shown that the combined use of

echocardiography and vascular ultrasound examinations has high effectiveness in the timely diagnosis of valve calcification, hemodynamic disturbances, and atherosclerotic processes.

Based on the obtained data, it became possible to identify patients belonging to high-risk groups and to assess the progression of degenerative processes at an early stage. The study results showed that timely correction of arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, and atherosclerosis may slow the development of valvular degeneration and vascular lesions.

Taking into account the clinical significance of echocardiography, the wide use of this method is recommended for screening and dynamic follow-up in elderly patients.

The study results may be used in cardiology and gerontology practice for individualized prevention, risk stratification, and selection of treatment tactics.

Conclusion

The results of the conducted study showed that degenerative changes in the heart valves and vascular system in elderly patients are interrelated and systemic in nature. Arterial hypertension, atherosclerosis, dyslipidemia, and diabetes mellitus were identified as leading pathogenetic factors in the development of degenerative processes.

Changes such as fibrosis, calcification, and thickening of the aortic valve, as well as regurgitation, incomplete closure, and fibrosis of the mitral valve, were detected at a high frequency. A close relationship was established between valve calcification and hemodynamic disturbances. In particular, a decrease in left ventricular pumping function was more frequently observed in patients with aortic stenosis.

The results of the correlation analysis confirmed the presence of a significant relationship between the duration of etiological factors and the severity of degenerative valvular changes. Long-term hemodynamic and metabolic influences played an important role in aortic valve lesions.

Atherosclerotic vascular lesions were often systemic in nature, with the coronary arteries recorded as the most frequently affected localization. In patients with multi-localized atherosclerosis, hemodynamic disturbances and the clinical course were more severe.

Echocardiography was confirmed to have high diagnostic value in the assessment of heart valves and hemodynamic changes. This method is of great importance in the early diagnosis of degenerative processes, identification of risk groups, and selection of individualized treatment tactics.

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